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CLIMATE RESILIENT AND ENVIRONMENTALLY
SUSTAINABLE TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE,
WITH A FOCUS ON INLAND WATERWAYS

D8.1 French River Pilot Specification and Baseline measurements

**CRISTAL - Climate resilient and environmentally sustainable transport
infrastructure, with a focus on inland waterways**

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List of abbreviations

Abbreviation/Term	Description
ADEME	French agency of ecological transition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIS	Automatic Identification System
BDO	Base de données des ouvrages (Infrastructure Database)
CMMS	Computerized Maintenance Management System
DTBS	Direction Territoriale Bassin de la Seine (Seine Basin territorial Direction)
DTNE	Direction Territoriale Nord-Est (North-East territorial Direction)
EEIG	European Economic Interest Grouping
EC	European Commission
GER	Gros Entretien Renouvellement (Major Maintenance and Renewal)
GIS	Geographic Information System
GPR	Ground Penetrating Radar
GPS	Global Positioning System
GPRS	General Packet Radio Service
GSM	Global System for Mobile communications
HAROPA	Le Havre – Rouen – Paris ports authority
ICC	International Chamber of Commerce
INRAE	Institut national de recherche pour l’agriculture, l’alimentation et l’environnement (National Institute for agriculture, food and environment investigation)
IoT	Internet of Things
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
IWT	Inland Waterways Transport
IWW	Inland Waterways
LoRaWAN	Radio communication protocol
MBF	Maintenance basée sur la fiabilité (Reliability Centered Maintenance, RMC)
POC	Proof Of Concept

RP	River Pilot
SCMS	Synchromodal Corridor Management System
VNF	Voies navigables de France
VTO	Visiteurs Techniques d’Ouvrage (technical reviewer of an asset)
WP	Work Package

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1. Executive Summary

This deliverable aims at defining the scope of French River Pilot: its objective, the different tools developed, the output measurement of these tools, and the results expected. All its work is developed inside WP8 of the CRISTAL Project.

French River Pilot is led by VNF which is an infrastructure manager that manages 80% of French Inland Waterways (IWW). In the context of the CRISTAL project, VNF has two objectives:

1. collect more reliable data on the use of its network.
2. improve the maintenance of its network.

These objectives are in alignment with CRISTAL project global objectives, tending to a more reliable IWW which creates an incentive for modal shift towards IWW.

The aims of the French River Pilot include developing tools to improve the management and maintenance of IWW within the pilot itself (CEDRE, Use of IoT and Smart Buoys), and testing/validating tools developed in other WPs (Synchronodal Corridor Management System, Digital Twin, Acoustic Emission SHM and Subsurface Radar Inspection).

This deliverable will detail the baseline scenario of the pilot, explaining its initial context. Then provide further details on the Pilot specification, explaining its objectives and how it is linked to the rest of the project. This is followed by the description of the execution plan and the outputs expected. Finally, the deliverable describes the expected results for French River Pilot and their baseline measurement.

1.1. Introduction

This deliverable has been developed for the CRISTAL project. Its aim is to detail the objectives of French River Pilot, to detail its execution plan, to evidence the research methodology and method of measurement of outputs, and to explain the expected results and their baseline measurement. French River Pilot is divided in two objectives: one being to collect more reliable data on the use of its network, and the other to improve maintenance. Both objectives are linked to the CRISTAL global objectives which are to improve the reliability of IWW transportation and increase its share in the different transport modes.

To achieve the first objective, VNF is developing two tools (T8.1 and T8.2). The first tool, aims at securing revenue linked to navigation duties applied to goods carried and at reducing the costs linked to the process of collecting and checking travel data while improving the logistic chain, thanks to the collection of data from freight forwarders or potentially shippers. The second tool aims at geolocating barges and know the availability of parking and handling areas.

To achieve the second objective, VNF is developing a tool and offers its network to test the technologies developed by the CRISTAL Project (T8.3; T8.4 and T8.5). The tool developed by VNF aims at geolocating the mooring buoys deployed on French canals and ensure they emit alerts when they drift, maintenance should be improved as well as security for IWW end-users. The pilot will also test two of the four technologies developed by CRISTAL project in WP2, as well as the technologies developed by WP5 and WP3.

1.2. Mapping Cristal outputs

CRISTAL GA Component Title	CRISTAL GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
D8.1 French RP Specification and Baseline measurements	<p><i>Report on French River Pilot assumptions including:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>Aim of pilot;</i> 2. <i>Assumptions for pilot execution;</i> 3. <i>Research methodology and measurement of outputs;</i> 4. <i>Expected results structure;</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Section 2 is developing the aim of the pilot and its baseline scenario. ○ Section 3 is developing French River Pilot specification. ○ Section 4 is developing French River Pilot Execution plan and the output expected. ○ Section 5 is developing the expected results, the baseline measurements, the assessment plan, the innovation plan and its expected impact 	This report aims at exploring the objectives and the realisation plan of French RP evidencing how it intends to achieve the objectives of the global project.
CORRESPONDING TASK(S)			
T8.1 Electronic freight documentation (CEDRE), a tool to optimize loadings	<p><i>Task 8.1 will aim to:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>Understand the needs of carriers, shippers and charterers (and also those of inland and sea ports).</i> 2. <i>Inventory the technical solutions available on the market (blockchain, AIS and other geolocation systems, dematerialization and use of certain commercial documents (river bill of lading, consignment note, etc.))</i> 3. <i>Gradually build a solution offering the best cost/benefit ratio for VNF and our customers. CEDRE makes it</i> 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Section 3.2.1.1: description of the objectives and expected outputs of the technologies developed. ○ Section 4.2.1: Execution plan of T8.1 	As this task is developing / testing / validating a technology, it is detailed in the present report.

	<p><i>possible to participate in the increase in the modal shift by 20% by offering a tool (provision of information for freight exchange) to optimize loadings (linking the needs of shippers with the space available in the ships on the forecast), as well than the 80% resilience (provision of information for freight exchange in times of crisis allowing the connection of shippers & apos; needs with the space available in the boats in forecast and in real time)</i></p> <p>4. Reform the freight toll, to introduce new concepts: new traffic (containers, heavy packages, urban logistics), the financial “weight” of the toll, the level of service offered by VNF on certain parts of the network.</p>		
T8.2 Use of IoT for the purposes of navigation facilitation and safety	<p>VNF Seine is carrying out various projects related to the use of IoT for the purposes of navigation facilitation and safety. A first series of these experiments takes place in the period 2021-2022. Following the analysis of the results of this first wave of experiments, a series of new experiments is planned to test devices that will complement the results. A sensor could be connected to the Digital twin (WP5) and to the Corridor Management (WP3).</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Section 3.2.1.2: description of the objectives and expected outputs of the technologies developed. ○ Section 4.2.2: Execution plan of T8.2 	<p>As this task is developing / testing / validating a technology, it is detailed in the present report.</p>
T8.3 Flood management on the Moselle River: use of smart buoys	<p><i>The buoys which delimit the navigation channel, are impacted when the currents are really strong and most peculiarly during and after floods. After a flood, the manager of the waterways (VNF) must be able to identify as quickly as possible which ones have left their place of anchorage and are going down the river in order to put them back in place as quickly as possible, to allow for a safe navigation. If it takes more time, it has to identify them and give</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Section 3.2.2.1: description of the objectives and expected outputs of the technologies developed. ○ Section 4.2.3: Execution plan for T8.3 	<p>As this task is developing / testing / validating a technology, it is detailed in the present report.</p>

	<p><i>the information to the users of the waterways. To do so, remote monitoring/remote management of the buoys and automation of information dissemination should be put in place. As an added-value of the overall system, buoys being able to automatically measure to water information on the changes in the water levels, preventing potential incidents and allowing for an optimisation of cargo management by the shipowners and the freight forwarders, increasing the inland navigation reliability and efficiency</i></p>		
<p>T8.4 Tools for predictive infrastructure maintenance</p>	<p><i>Land based and Vessel Mounted Subsurface Inspection Radar Technology (WP2) – technology transfer from the rail sector to develop a vessel mounted IWW infrastructure subsurface inspection system to determine the maintenance issues with IWW features for planned maintenance. The data collected can be used to develop IWW infrastructure digital twins, comparison with the benchmark will reveal changes in the infrastructures for predictive infrastructure maintenance. This Task builds on WP2, which developed a tailored approach to the subsurface inspection of IWW critical infrastructure. It simply addresses the global challenge of how to maintain IWW infrastructures through non-destructive examination.</i></p> <p><i>This inspection system will inspect VNF infrastructure. Land based and Vessel Mounted Subsurface Inspection Radar Technology - technology transfer from the rail sector to develop a vessel mounted IWW infrastructure subsurface inspection system to determine the maintenance issues with IWW features for planned maintenance.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Section 3.2.2.2: description of the objectives and expected outputs of the technologies developed. ○ Section 4.3.1: Execution plan for T8.4 	<p>As this task is developing / testing / validating a technology, it is detailed in the present report.</p>

	<p><i>The data collected can be used to develop IWW infrastructure digital twins, comparison with the benchmark will reveal changes in the infrastructures. This inspection system will then be used for the inspection of the infrastructure in the French Pilot. The head of Moselle maintenance has identified a need to inspect interior cavities, internal erosion, interior water flows, sub-cavities for the following types of structures: sheet piling, rock walls, open trenches, retaining walls, embankments, concrete slab/ceiling and locks. The data collected will provide the information to use predictive models to determine the residual life of these structures. The primary target for critical infrastructure subsurface inspection are the locks on the Moselle River. VNF will provide a sealed empty lock without water for inspection with the EUMO system. An empty lock on Moselle is 180m long x 12 m width x (10 m to 15 m) high the demonstration will be in June 2024. EUMO will collect the data and UNEW will provide 3D subsurface visualisations of the lock walls and foundation. VNF will use this information to support the modernisation program. It is also possible that small inland waterway locks may be included in the inspection trials as they are thought to be in need of repair.</i></p>		
<p>T8.5 Corridor management</p>	<p><i>Corridor management (WP3) system will be tested for “ice jams” (Seine), water (Seine, Moselle) and traffic management (CEDRE)</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Section 3.2.3 description of the technology objectives and outputs in the context of French River Pilot ○ Section 4.3.3: Execution plan for T8.5 	<p>As this task is developing / testing / validating a technology, it is detailed in the present report.</p>

<p>T8.6 Governance</p>	<p><i>Living Labs (WP4) will be tested for “ice jams” (Seine), water (Moselle) and traffic management (CEDRE)</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Section 3.1 description of the context of French River Pilot ○ Section 4.1: Execution plan for T8.6 	<p>As this task is developing / testing / validating a technology, it is detailed in the present report.</p>
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1.3. Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

Deliverable 8.1 is divided in **4 mains sections**:

- **Section 2** examines the baseline scenarios of the Lower Seine and Downstream Moselle regions, providing insights into their current conditions and objectives. Logistics, stakeholders, maintenance descriptions, and a SWOT analysis are explored to provide a comprehensive overview of the French River Pilot Baseline scenario.
- Transitioning to **section 3**, the report details the specification of the pilot, emphasising on its objectives. It starts with an overview of the stakeholders involved in the French RP. Then this section details first the tools developed in order to improve data reliability into the pilot and also details the tools developed in order to improve maintenance. Finally, this section ends by developing the information systems and how it can feed the two main productions of the CRISTAL Project: the Digital Twin and the Synchronodal Corridor Management System.
- In **section 4**, the report outlines the execution plan for the pilot project and the outputs expected. It details the technologies and tools developed, including their functionalities and applications.
- **Section 5** of the document delves into the anticipated results of French River Pilot and how they will be assessed. Key performance indicators (KPIs) and an assessment plan are defined to evaluate the project's success as well as an innovation plan with its expected impacts.

The remaining sections are the Introductory section (Section 1) and the Conclusions, as well as the References, Lists of tables and figures, and Annexes.

2. French River Pilot Baseline situation and objectives

This section is dedicated at describing and explaining the baseline situation of the French pilot. This description provides the context for the aims and objectives of the pilot, that can be found in the next section.

2.1. Pilot Case Baseline scenario

The French pilot is made up of two waterways: the Lower Seine and the Moselle, that are part of the waterway network managed by VNF, shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Map of VNF network with gauge detail (source: VNF).

2.1.1. Lower Seine

The Seine serves as a crucial waterway, linking the first national port complex, HAROPA (comprising the ports of Le Havre, Rouen and Paris), to the Ile-de-France region, France's largest urban area and one of Europe's most populous.

The river plays a significant role in the transportation of goods within this vital economic zone, facilitating the movement of construction materials, agricultural and energy products, various containerized goods, waste, vehicles, and heavy packages. Despite its current usage, the Seine's potential is far from fully realized (Dehus, C., August 2020). As an underutilized transport infrastructure, the Seine could handle four times its current traffic volume. It offers a viable and environmentally friendly alternative to road freight transport, strengthening the position of the Seine axis ports and promoting their hinterland development.

Stretching 233 km from Rouen to Paris, the Lower Seine is a large-gauge class Vb river (as per the European classification of waterways), open to navigation 24 hours a day. It can accommodate barges up to 185 meters long, carrying up to 4,400 tonnes of goods, equivalent to 220 trucks. On average, between 10,000 and 16,000 ships pass through the Seine's locks annually, with freight ships making up 85% of this traffic (Canal, G. & Chevandier, T., May 2021, p.55).

The river's traffic is facilitated by a high level of service, both physical and digital. However, improvements are needed to cater to the waterway's multifunctionality. Ensuring the Lower Seine axis maintains minimum performance conditions is crucial for the river's two primary functions: navigation and hydraulic management. Maintaining these functions necessitates not only a well-maintained infrastructure but also real-time monitoring, short-term operational forecasting, and coordinated and optimized management of traffic, structures, and water levels.

Figure 2: Map of the Seine Basin network, with territorial division detail (source: VNF).

2.1.2. Moselle

The large gauge Moselle (class V), running over 158 km, allows the passage of self-propelled and pushed convoys of more than 3,000 tons to the North Sea ports via the Rhine (DTNE, 2006). Other waterways of Freycinet gauge (corresponding to Class I of the European classification) and accessible to commercial navigation converge towards the Moselle, thus having a possible role of feeder lanes. It directly serves two major cities (Metz and Nancy), the industrial basins of Thionville, Pont-à-Mousson and the Saar basin. It has public and private ports, including the port of Metz (9th in France with 2,183,000 tonnes in 2019, first French port for cereals) (VNF, 2019).

Overflow (floods) can indirectly impact navigation with hazards such as driftwood or landings, as well as movement of markings. These hazards also generate disturbances. The number of phenomena impacting navigation remains constant from 3 to 4 per year. The possible flood period also tends to extend (late autumn and the start of winter) (Cerema, February 2021).

Figure 3: Map of North-East territorial Direction of VNF.
(Source: VNF).

Measures are taken during the low water period: from beginning of July to end of October (or even December). VNF has always faced difficulties in regulating flows on the Moselle. Indeed, for low to medium flows, flow waves are observed propagating upstream to downstream of the Moselle.

The regulation for both dams and hydroelectric plants consists of maintaining as closely as possible the regulation level set upstream of each dam. This mode of regulation does not make possible to reduce the flow waves, in some cases it even accentuates them. The mode of operation can accentuate wave

phenomena: this is largely due to problems of interactions between dams and hydroelectric power stations over which VNF has no control (unlike our German or Luxembourg counterparts who are in control of hydroelectric power). Regulation, taking into account an improvement in flow regulation, will lead to a greater tidal range around the regulation level upstream of the dams.

For each reach, in addition to the already formalized ‘target’ regulation range, a maximum admissible high and low level for the level upstream of the dams should be defined. These ratings would take into account the needs for navigation, i.e. the minimum draft for ships below bridges and the channel depth for ship draught.

2.2. Logistics

In most cases on French network, clients are shippers from various industries, purchasing transportation services from ship-owners, but more often through charterers, whose job is to find barges available at the right time and location. This way of proceeding involves a wide range of industries such as: sand and gravels, grain, bulk waste, breakbulk cargo, etc.

In this sort of business, other companies may also act as purchasers of IWT. Freight forwarders or shipping companies, as well as road haulage companies wishing to switch part of their range of services to CO2 low emissions modes of transport, are in direct contact with a client, and instead of restricting their service to their own know-how (stevedoring) they sometimes offer a port-to-port service (meaning they charter barges on a single voyage or tonnage basis) or even sometimes door to door.

This practically means that barges are the property of three possible profiles:

- In most cases, barge owners (who own 1 to 4 barges as an individual, but this number may reach several hundred in some cases),
- In more particular cases, in specific industries such as sand & gravel production where logistics costs are a key point, producers may own a few dozen barges and a few pushers (in France, there are two such companies owning, each of them, around one hundred barges and about ten pushers),
- Finally, due to lack of barges available (especially in the current context in Europe) some shippers choose to invest in their own fleet. VNF operates a subsidies program providing them with financial support for such purchases.

Containers are carried on inland waterways by container barging operators, who charter barges from shipowners, mostly on a time charter basis, in order to offer port-to-port services with regular schedules. In some cases, those container barging operators own their own barges, but this is seldom the case.

In the same way, city distribution barging services are managed by multimodal freight forwarders, who most of the time charter the barges but, in some cases may also own them, and include them in their final kilometre delivery, nearly always with cargo e-bikes.

Traffic

As a result of the pandemic, the 2020 results for river freight activity shows a drop of – 10.7% in tonnes, i.e., 50.9 million tonnes transported and – 11.6% in t-km, i.e. nearly 6.6 billion tonne-kilometres (t-km). The river dynamic initiated in 2019 (+10.0 in t-km) was slowed down by the pandemic (E2F, 26 March 2021). However, maintaining its 2018 level, and compared to other modes of transport, the change remains weak, demonstrating the resilience and adaptability demonstrated by the river sector. In 2021, river traffic was up by 3.8% in t-km over the year compared to 2020. Despite the Covid crisis, traffic exceeded the level of 2018 (+1.1% in t-km) (E2F, 26 March 2021).

Traffic volumes on the French pilot sites have been for the past twenty years relatively stable in the Seine Basin at around 20 million tonnes per year, however, volumes in the North-East Basin have lost almost half from 10 million tonnes (2000) to 5,7 million tonnes in 2018, affected by a drop in mineral fuels. The Seine Basin is dominated by Crude materials including building materials, influenced by the large port of Rouen being a multi-modal port, which specialising in bulk and agri-bulk commodities. The North-East Basin demonstrates a considerable number of agricultural products (VNF, 2022).

2.3. Stakeholders

Table 1: Pilot's stakeholders' classification (Source: VNF).

Scope of the total transport network for the pilot			
	Main stakeholders	Description	French Pilot
Transport function	Infrastructure manager		
		Rail	SNCF réseau
		Road	SANEF/SAPN, région Grand Est
		IWT	VNF, Compagnie Nationale du Rhône and EDF, French main power supplier
	Transport companies		
		Shipping lines	CFT, CFNR, ELV/NPRC, containers barges operators
		Trucks	Mauffrey/MGE/Transports Vigneron/Transports Foulon
		rail freight operators	SNCF + others
		barge operators	HGK, Haeger&Schmidt, NPRC, Rhenus, MAFF, Transtest, Specherei...
	Inland terminals		
	Terminal operators	Seine: Haropa, Moselle: The company managing the whole is a private company appointed by VNF after a public tender; the public logistics operator is a long-term lease contract operator	

	Deepsea ports		
		Terminal operators	Terminaux de Normandie, Générale de Manutention Portuaire, etc.
		Port authorities	Seine: Haropa
	Logistics service providers		
		1 PL (producer delivers cargo to client, own trucks/vessels)	HLafarge Holcim, Cemex, Volta, ...
		2 PL (producer delivers cargo via transport company)	CFT, SCAT, Coalis, transports Blanchet, ELV-NPRC, etc.
		3PL (outsourcing of logistics to a third party)	same as hereabove
		4PL (outsource all of the organisation and oversight of their supply chain and logistics to one external provider which has no own assets)	HGK, Haeger&Schmidt, NPRC, Rhenus, MAFF, Transest, Specherei...
		5PL ('= 4PL + view on network rather than chain)	
		Shippers / cargo owners	
		Senders	
		Receivers	
Regulation	Regulators of IWT		
		EU	Yes
		Government	Ministry in charge of transportation, tourism, energy transition ; Agence de l'environnement et de la maîtrise de l'énergie (public funding organism).
		Local government	Le Havre district organisation, métropole du Grand Nancy, CCNR, CIM (International Commission of the Moselle), some inter-cities local governments
Public interest	People		
		Citizens living near the waterways	
		environmental group(s)	France Nature Environnement, or more depending on requirements
		Local interest groups	

Linked industries to IWT	Sector organisations representing private companies		
		Farmers	
		Power plants	Syndicat des énergies renouvelables
		Tourism sector	
		Transport sector	Entreprises fluviales de France ; Union des Chargeurs de Lorraine ; Organisation des PME du transport routier ; Association des utilisateurs de transport de fret ; Union des transporteurs publics et ferroviaires ; Fédération nationale des transports routiers, Organisation des Transporteurs Routiers Européens (OTRE) ; Union des Entreprises de Transport et de Logistique de France
Researchers	Universities		
		University1	
		University2	
	Knowledge institutes		
		Knowledge institute 1	EM Normandie
	Knowledge institute 2	Neoma Rouen	

Commitments for green growth

To preserve the ecological advantage of the river, there are numerous initiatives and experiments in terms of greening: electric motorization, natural gas or even hydrogen.

Voies navigables de France, as the national inland waterways operator, is increasing its initiatives to support the sector in this challenge and enable it to strengthen its ecological performance.

It is therefore quite natural that VNF signed in July 2021 Commitments for Green Growth with the State, E2F (Entreprises Fluviales de France: France Inland waterways Companies) and economic operators in the sector (Ministère de la Transition Ecologique et de la Cohésion des Territoires, 7 July 2021). These aim at:

- reducing river GHG emissions by 20% within 10 years;
- promote the implementation of shore power supply station with an overall target of 150 electric terminals on the quay by 2024;
- experiment with alternative low-emission motorization solutions and facilitating experiments in innovative motorization, in particular with the support of the Fleet Modernization and Innovation Assistance Plan (PAMI) implemented by VNF.

AUTF Partnership

VNF and the Association of Freight Transport Users (AUTF) signed a partnership agreement on September 2021, which aims at accelerating the conversion of shippers to clean logistics as part of the ReMoVe program, financed by the EC, and particularly to logistics river (AUTF, September 2021).

VNF/SNCF Network partnership

January 26, 2021, was marked by the signing of the national VNF-SNCF Réseau agreement, which notably provides for joint actions to develop multimodal rail/river flows (VNF, January 2021).

The collaboration between SNCF Réseau and VNF continued with 5 territorial partnerships signed in 2021 and 2022 in these sectors: Seine Axis, Rhône-Saône Axis, North-East, Hauts de France and Strasbourg Grand Est.

Partnership for river transport on the Seine with Haropa

On the occasion of a webinar "River Logistics Axis Seine" for economic actors in November 2021, VNF and HAROPA PORT signed a partnership agreement for the development of river transport on the Seine (Haropa Port, 10 November 2021). The competitiveness of the supply chain as well as the ecological and energy transition are at the heart of the objectives of this partnership.

Signature of a port partnership agreement

A commitment agreement for stakeholders in French supply chains was signed in the presence of the Minister for the Sea and the Minister Delegate for Transport in October 2020 (Ministère de la Transition Ecologique et de la Cohésion des Territoires, 8 October 2020). This agreement is a major opportunity to promote intermodality and mass transport.

2.4. Maintenance

Improving the availability of the river network is a strategic focus for VNF. This ambition is materialized in particular through the implementation of an asset management policy including a specialized preventive maintenance policy, which must constitute a real lever for improving the reliability of network structures and routes, with a view to increase their availability (Sector Group, 2012). VNF is constantly looking for new tools to improve its control over its network, to improve maintenance efficiency and to reduce maintenance costs. Currently, the official VNF target is for preventive maintenance to represent 70% of global maintenance compared to corrective maintenance (VNF & MTE, 20 December 2023). Preventive maintenance is the maintenance done to avoid failures while corrective maintenance is done to repair failures. Repairing is judged more expensive by VNF and corrective maintenance usually induce an interruption of traffic which is VNF aims at avoiding as much as possible.

Currently asset management encompasses the following actions:

1. the maintenance of assets (discrete and linear works), i.e. all the technical, administrative and management actions during the life cycle of an asset, intended to maintain it or restore it in a state in which it can perform the required function;
2. asset monitoring, i.e. the activity, carried out manually or automatically, aimed at observing the actual state of the infrastructure; monitoring differs from inspection in that it is used to assess changes in infrastructure parameters over time; monitoring is an integral part of asset maintenance;
3. asset inspection, i.e. the compliance check carried out by measuring, observing, testing or calibrating the significant characteristics of the infrastructure;
4. major maintenance and renewal (GER) of assets, i.e. the action of regenerating part of a piece of equipment or equipment, or the action of major maintenance of long-term equipment, carried out with the aim of increasing the life of the good;
5. assessment of the state of the asset and its monitoring.

Maintenance program

Annual shutdown is the period during which Voies navigables de France carries out maintenance, renovation and modernization work to make the network more reliable and improve the service offer. The annual maintenance program is agreed with users, at local and national level, then proposed for deliberation by the VNF board of directors. Afterwards, the calendar of shutdowns is made public and can be found on VNF website. This data is as well included in the French RIS (River Information Service) and can be found on EuRIS, the European platform gathering all the European RISs. The shutdown map is revised each year (IGN, 2023).

Asset management policy

VNF's asset management policy has in particular materialized through:

- The establishment of a national database of works, aiming at managing, updating and administering in a shared and homogeneous manner the national inventory of infrastructure works and reaches as well as the qualification of their functional state,
- The definition of Preventive Maintenance Plans and associated operating ranges, on the works.

National Books Database

The Infrastructure Database (BDO) is an operational and strategic management tool for VNF's infrastructure assets. Its fundamental objective is to capitalize the data of this asset in a centralized and common tool, shared and harmonized at the national level, in order to:

- quickly have information on one or more works, and regularly update,
- facilitate access to and sharing of data,
- allow data to be processed to extract useful summaries for analysis or decision support, by structure, by type of structure, by route, by DT, etc.

To fill in this database, and in particular the decomposition and functional state of the structures, a visit method has been developed to:

- assess the state of the functions (example: navigation, maintenance of the body of water, etc.) performed by a structure,
- recommend intervention actions on the structure.

The qualification of the functional state of the asset serves as a support for the risk analysis of the works and then for the definition of the policy for prioritizing investment programs at the national level.

The BDO gives a "snapshot" of the knowledge and state of the assets, according to a harmonized national method. The qualification of the condition of a structure is based on a visual inspection of a structure in operation, and therefore generally in water.

The BDO is based on simple, quick, and harmonized visits to the structures with a view to establish the strategy for managing the river infrastructure heritage. It does not dispense with operational management (concrete actions for rehabilitation, maintenance) and regulatory works.

The BDO is neither a work inspection, nor a diagnosis, nor an exhaustive evaluation of the work to be carried out or a CMMS (Computerized Maintenance Management System). It does not replace the checks and monitoring imposed by regulations or by security requirements.

A Technical Inspection of Works (VTO) is carried out by a person trained in the inventory methodology and qualification of VNF's assets. This person is called a Technical Structures Visitor.

The Technical Structures Visitor is not necessarily a specialist or expert in all the fields (civil engineering, electromechanical, electricity, etc.) concerned by the visit. For the visit, the Technical Structures Visitor must be, if possible (mandatory if an external service provider), accompanied by the operator who preferably has a certain knowledge of the structure.

The VTO is carried out over a limited time (varying from half a day to 1 or 2 days depending on the complexity and size of the work). It is based on observations (mostly visual) at the time of the visit and on the statements of the operator. During the VTO, no measurements, sampling or tests are carried out. The VTO is not a structural diagnosis. The objective of the VTO is to qualify the functional state of a structure.

Preventive maintenance

Preventive maintenance must allow to maintain over time the performance of the structures that the investments in repair will have, if necessary, made possible to improve. VNF consider that preventive maintenance is cheaper than corrective maintenance, as preventive maintenance allows planning, organisation and costs control, while corrective maintenance happens in emergency conditions, often inducing an interruption of traffic and with no control over the costs. For VNF, preventive maintenance is preferable and is planned.

The preventive maintenance plan summarizes the components of the management of a given structure by maintenance. It specifies the preventive interventions as well as their parameters (nature, frequency, load, etc.).

The analysis leading to the preventive maintenance plans must take into account all the actions contributing to the maintenance of the structures, independently of the stakeholders (operator, maintainer, external company, etc.), namely:

- routine maintenance of work equipment,
- monitoring and maintenance of current cleanliness,
- routine preventive maintenance, including regulatory actions (particularly related to electrical installations, lifting devices and pressure vessels, etc.),
- Major Maintenance and Renewal (GER)

VNF uses the MBF method also called RMC (Reliability Centred Maintenance) to ensure that preventive maintenance, as the receptacle of a structured preventive approach, guarantees an optimal quality of service when applied scrupulously.

The MBF method aims to build a preventive maintenance plan “going to the essentials”, from the evaluation of the criticality of the equipment. It is also suitable for optimizing existing preventive maintenance plans, based on the use of feedback.

The MBF method is completed by an approach to define the so-called “strategic” stock. This is the stock of parts whose unavailability may have consequences deemed “unacceptable” on the quality of service. An MBF analysis aims to size (or specify) the maintenance effort based on the consequences (notions of severity/frequency) of failures (approach by “function”) and not according to the failures themselves (approach by “equipment “).

“Function” approach

The MBF is therefore a working method whose result is a preventive maintenance plan, which makes it possible to avoid both under-quality and over-quality in maintenance. For a given piece of equipment, a structured preventive maintenance plan contains:

- the preventive maintenance tasks and the periodicities of intervention,
- information on the implementation of these tasks [status of the structure (on/off) to carry out the task, trade concerned, estimated duration of the task and the spare parts required].

The development of preventive maintenance plans is adapted to the scale of a structure. In general, the scope of a study, aimed at producing or optimizing a preventive maintenance plan, covers all the equipment of the structure.

It is possible that the development of the preventive maintenance plan anticipates scheduled changes to the structure (restoration, replacement of equipment, change of technology, etc.). In this case, it is important to build the preventive maintenance plan by analysing and also integrating the impact of the changes on the content of the preventive maintenance plan.

The analysis leading to the preventive maintenance plans must take into account all the actions contributing to the maintenance of the structures, independently of the stakeholders (operator, maintainer, external company, etc.), namely:

- Routine maintenance of work equipment,
- Monitoring and maintenance of current cleanliness,
- Routine preventive maintenance, including regulatory actions (particularly related to electrical installations, lifting devices and pressure vessels, etc.),
- Major Maintenance and Renewal (GER*).

* GER: all operations to renew equipment or part of equipment, or major maintenance actions for long-life equipment, carried out with the aim of increasing the life of a good.

An MBF study produces three documents:

- The preventive maintenance plan for a given structure,
- The list of strategic spare parts attached to the structure,
- Actions aimed at improving the reliability of the structure and improving maintenance practices.

The preventive maintenance plan is built based on the expertise of the agents intervening “on a daily basis” on the structure; the technical relevance of the preventive maintenance plan is therefore ensured. The list of strategic spare parts identifies the parts whose unavailability may have consequences deemed "unacceptable" on the quality of service.

Finally, the MBF study, based on a criticality analysis, can highlight specific actions to improve the structures or maintenance practices.

Updating and optimizing preventive maintenance plans is a continuous process, the MBF is a tool that accompanies the evolution of preventive maintenance plans. Periodic reviews of MBF studies must be undertaken to judge the effectiveness of the preventive maintenance plan and to optimize it again, in a logic of continuous improvement of practices. Optimization is carried out based on feedback, the evolution of the works and the context. However, it is necessary to let the preventive maintenance plans operate long enough, around 2 to 3 years, so that they can bring the benefits of their optimization.

It should be noted that the MBF method is not a method to be used in an emergency situation or following a failure. It is a method that focuses on the medium/long term.

THE MBF METHOD:

The MBF method is based on the following four questions, each corresponding to a method step:

- **Step 1: How do the facilities work?**

It is the analysis of the functioning.

Sub-step 1.1: find the hardware limits of the studied system

Sub-step 1.2: find the main function(s) of the system

Sub-step 1.3: decomposing the system into Functional Groupings

- **Step 2: How are the installations malfunctioning?**

This is the analysis of malfunctions.

Sub-step 2.1: Failure Mode

Sub-step 2.2: Detectability

Sub-step 2.3: Effects

Sub-step 2.4: Pair Maintainable Unit / Cause

Sub-step 2.5: Criticality

Sub-step 2.6: Current preventive maintenance

- **Step 3: How to counter the failures having the most critical consequences?**

This is the choice of preventive maintenance tasks.

Sub-step 3.1: Maintenance Orientations

Sub-step 3.2: Choice of maintenance tasks

Sub-step 3.3: Characterization of proposed tasks

- **Step 4: How to define the strategic stock of spare parts?**

This is the list of the defined strategic stock selected by category.

Lock type breakdown

Civil engineering - airlock

Mooring (mooring post, etc.)

Side wall

Chamber door / leaf

Goldfinch

Coronation

Access ladder

Fall wall

Guard wall

Surge protector

Write off

Civil engineering - upstream or downstream head

Aqueduct (upstream / downstream / bypass / supply / control / filling ...)

Level measuring device (limnometric scale, scale level ...)

Comb

Pit jacks / rack

Trailing wall

Bullnose

Rock rip-rap

Portico (light support, cable passage, pipes, etc.)

Write off

Guide rails

Cofferdam grooves

Stairs

Platform

Door

Joints

Bridge

Structure

Sealing system

Manoeuvring system

Lock system

Airlock filling and emptying system

Vanes (including manoeuvring system) or valves

Reach regulation

Vanes (including manoeuvring system) or valves

Filling

Vanes (including manoeuvring system) or valves

Emptying

Reach regulation system

Weir

Deviation

Power supply

Emergency power supply (generator, etc.)

Transformers

TGBT / HV cell

HV/LV distribution

Cabinet (structure)

Cabinet (power)

Cabinet (protection of goods and people)

Control system (including automation)

Dedicated backup power (UPS)

Automation

Sensors

Cabinet (control, relay)

Communication (cables, cards, ...)

Telecommunications (telephony, radios, teletransmission, audio, etc.)

HM interface (touch screen, display, box, control panel)

User/structure communication system

Hydraulic central

Tarpaulin

Motor pump

Emergency system (auxiliary electric or manual pump, etc.)

Control of distribution devices

Hydraulic distribution

Piping / Hoses

Signage, surveillance, and security

Navigation lights

Information panels

Navigation panels

Audible and visual signal

Video surveillance

Buoy

Markings on the ground

Bodyguard

Means of communication

PC call intercom

Radio

Microphone / HP

Building

Shelter, technical room, operating building

Control cabin

Living space

Lighting

Building lighting

Lighting of the work

Public lighting

Others

Dolphins

Floating body removal device (crane, screen, etc.)

Site fencing devices

2.5. SWOT Analysis

This SWOT has been realised in the framework of WP1 considering the project objective “a resilient inland waterway infrastructure for transport”. This SWOT portrays the context in which the CRISTAL Project intervenes for the French River Pilot.

Strength

- Thanks to its nature of being a public entity and its organisation, VNF is deeply committed and equipped towards innovation.
- Its organisation, divided in different territorial route units, allows proximity with local actors, enabling better reactivity for crisis management.
- Currently, inland waterways logistics is increasing: +9.8% in 2019 compared to 2018, after a continued decrease since 2013. The sector is marked by a decrease of 11.4% in 2020 compared to 2019 due to the Covid Crisis but is increasing again (4%) in 2021 (Statistiques publiques, March 2023).
- Indeed, as Lionel Rouillon, Development Director of VNF, explained, inland waterways transport is highly competitive (Rouillon, November-December 2022).
 - By its price: the price of large-scale inland waterway transport, reported to the Tkm is the cheapest.
 - By CO2 emission: it produces 5 times less by tonne transported than road transport.
 - By its reliability: no congestion reported on French or European inland waterway network can be compared to a disturbance (it means that the congestion does not cost between 4.5 and 12.8€ / 1000Tkm transported). French network availability is about 98%, which is far superior to any other transport mode. Inland waterways transport offers a transport with no risk of congestion and if this is coupled with a floating stock, it is the best transport mode to face demand surges, it is the perfect mode for “just in time” supply chains.
 - By its security: very few thefts or accidents are reported on IWT, it is the safest.

- Financially, the biggest part of the studies, tests, running-in periods and investments are financed by VNF and ReMoVe program (ADEME, AUTF, TLF, E2F, VNF, UTP, cluster maritime français, FNTR and OTRE).
- VNF is preparing an increase of the use of IWT (VNF, 14 June 2021).
- Several projects are ongoing to increase the large gauge proportion in IW French network: the objective is to reach 2200 km and to increase its capacity to a maximum of 5000 tonnes by journey. Works on the Seine to link it with the Northern Europe network should increase IWT by 65%, and many other works are ongoing (canal Condé-Pommeroeul, Lys canal, etc.) in the framework of the Seine-Scheldt project, the largest inland waterways network in Europe.
- New services are developed by VNF in order to make the network more user friendly and more efficient (EURIS, NAVI or CEDRE).
- To enhance motorisation and modernisation, VNF has been equipped with 100m€ until 2030.
- Several projects are developed in order to be as innovative as possible: concerning alternative fuels, green energies production, energy consumption optimization, autonomous vessels and new logistics models in urban areas, etc.
- Finally, the more intense and more frequent droughts predicted are seriously considered by VNF, which developed the resilience of its network, managing 50 reservoir dams generating a reserve of 150 million m³.

Weaknesses:

- Inland waterways logistics are often considered as too complicated. Indeed, it mobilises several professions: road transporter for pre and post routing, terminal operators, warehousemen, refiners, inland waterway carrier, etc. Freight forwarders are often misinformed about IWT advantages and ways of working.
- The network is currently too small, in France, massification of IWT means developing large gauge canals. It is ongoing but not ready for now (only 2000 km for now).
- Infrastructures are often in bad conditions (dating from the 60's for large gauge and from the 19th century for small gauge).
- Maintenance is not optimized currently as it is under controlled nationally. Often, VNF is not the owner but only the manager of the infrastructure; it limits the possibilities to comply with environmental issues.

Opportunities:

- Container transport expansion, specifically on the Seine basin is a potential source of development.
- Increase of recycled building waste in production of building materials (target: 30% by 2030) (VNF, 14 June 2021).
- Supply chain is improving, thus enabling new clients to enter the market.

- By a strong effort of education with the development of RiverLearning training, and the support of important feeders and organisations like AUTF and TLF (sector organisations), new transport agents got into IWT, along with new shippers.
- ReMoVe program (2023-2025) consists of two parts: one dedicated to greening the fleet (Log-TE) and the other one focusing on modal shift (ReMo): it includes a specific budget (50% of its 38,5 M€ budget) dedicated to an incentive for new modal shift projects (in order to reduce pre/post trucking costs as well as handling costs) (VNF, December 2022).
- Political decisions have been made in order to improve IWT competitiveness, like the development of the infrastructure in Le Havre or Fos, or the modification of the prices in Dunkerque, with CMA CGM that erased part of the handling cost difference to equalize costs between all transport modes, giving VNF opportunities to IWT penetration.
- Many ports in France are reaching the end of the concession period, enabling the possibility to enhance competitiveness.
- There is a lack of trucks drivers.
- Increasing environmental minded inquiries from shippers
- A new agreement has been made between VNF and SNCF Réseau, the main railway operator in France, enabling multimodal transportation.
- New politics of GHGs emissions and climate change adaptation have been made by the government, VNF is modernising its network in accordance with them, and water managers, many opportunities are available.

The CRISTAL Project is an opportunity to pool European data, to pool the development, maintenance and improvement of information systems (infrastructures, AI, software, decision support systems, etc.), to standardise, to speed up partnerships, etc.

Threats:

- French industry is declining and under strong international competence, with the context of energy crisis and economic, social and environmental dumping of non-European countries.
- Road transport competitiveness has increased since 1970.
- Part of the current fleet on IW network is old and needs to be modernised as Lionel Rouillon, Development Director of VNF explained, to do so, 1000 to 1500m € are necessary by 2030. VNF can finance 75% of this cost, but 150 to 300m€ still needs to be found (Rouillon, November-December 2022)
- Around 2070, experts anticipate a general decrease of water flow, which would diminish the recharge between 10 and 25% (Stollsteiner, 2012). VNF needs to manage water flow.
- Flooding episodes are more and more violent, which increase risks on hydraulic structures.
- Health and economic crisis disorganised the supply chain and may continue in the future.
- With no financial autonomy and no multi annual programming, VNF's actions management is difficult.
- In VNF, recruiting and training is difficult, inducing a lack of human resources.
- There is an increasing lack of barge skippers, lack of new entrepreneurs.

- During crisis management, as help in operational decisions is not optimal, situations can become complicated for operation and maintenance.
- VNF noticed an explosion in invasive alien species, endangering small gauge canals.
- Environmental requirements make it difficult to realise VNF's mission, thereby diminishing its competitiveness.
- Cybersecurity is becoming a real threat as an increase in attacks have been observed. It is even more concerning considering the modernisation and digitalisation of VNF network.
- With energy crisis, water pumping is becoming more expensive, and it is necessary for some artificial canals, making high the risk of failure to supply.

3. Pilot specification

French pilot has two objectives: improving the reliability of the data collected on its network and improving the maintenance of its network, both in order to provide better services and a more reliable network to its end-users, even if an incident occurs. To do so, French pilot is testing different tools.

Indeed, as described in the precedent section, both Seine and Moselle can welcome a bigger share of freight. Seine River has underutilized transport infrastructure with a potential that is not fully realized while Moselle River suffers a constant decrease of volumes transported. Both rivers need to improve its attractivity and offering new services is a way to do so. The SCMS, CEDRE or the use of IOT are tools that will offer a better service to the end-user, with the aim to increase the modal share of IWW in fine.

Moreover, both river infrastructures need to improve maintenance, to cater waterway's multifunctionality or to improve flood regulation. Indeed, VNF needs to always ensure a minimum performance condition. For that, real-time monitoring, operational forecasting, management of traffic are all necessary to secure a well-maintained infrastructure. DT, SIR, AE, smart buoys and CEDRE are tools that will help achieving those objectives.

This section is dedicated at explaining the objective of the pilot action by action. The detailed plan for the actions will be developed in the next section.

3.1. Pilot stakeholders to be involved in French River pilot Living Lab

French pilot is divided in two objectives: provide a better service to the end-user of Inland waterways while improving the reliability of the data collected and improving the maintenance of its network. This is why the pilot is divided between different types of actors. The technology providers, the inland waterways end-users, and the infrastructure managers and regulators. These different stakeholders will be involved in the Living Lab activities in order to ensure the accordance of the developed-by-Cristal tools finality with their needs.

Table 2: French pilot stakeholders detailed (source: VNF).

Scope IWT management system for the pilot			
	Main actors	Detailed actors	French Pilot
Transport function	Infrastructure manager		
		IWT	VNF
	Transport companies		
		Barge operators	CFT, Coalis, SCAT, transports Lalemant, transports Blanchet, Cemex, Lafarge-Holcim, Marfret ; VNF is currently discussing with 5 other freight forwarders/shippers. They represent 70 to 80% of fret IWT in France.
	Tech provider		
	Supplier 1 of WP2 technology		UNEW, Euromobilita

		Supplier 2 of WP2 technology	CERTH
		WP3 partners developing the SCMS	CERTH
		WP5 partners developing the Digital Twin	Fraunhofer
Regulation	Regulators of IWT		
		EU	
		Federal government	VNF, Cellule ministérielle de veille opérationnelle et d'alerte
		Local government	

3.2. The objectives of the tools developed and tested in River Pilot France

The French River Pilot can be divided in two global objectives: gather more reliable data for the end-user of IWW and the infrastructure manager, and develop tools to ease maintenance for the infrastructure managers. Those two objectives aim at completing the global CRISTAL project objectives which are to increase IWT modal share and to increase IWT reliability. The first part of this section will be dedicated to the tools aiming at developing a more reliable data, the second part will be dedicated to maintenance purposes, the third part will develop the expectations regarding the DT and the SCMS and their links with VNF's information system.

3.2.1. Tools to improve the reliability of data on French network

In this first section CEDRE and use of IoT are the two tools that will be described, as VNF is currently developing it inside the CRISTAL project. Their objective is to create more data on logistics on French network. This data will become more reliable and will be of use of IWW users as well as for the infrastructure manager. This data once collected can feed DT and SCMS in real time.

3.2.1.1 *CEDRE, a tool to simplify administrative formalities and optimize loading (France, Europe)*

CEDRE aims at improving the current platform called VELI that is used to collect data on the cargo transported on French network.

Currently the system fails in different aspects: there is no automatic communication, data collected is not available at the European ERINOT format. More importantly, the formality required is of no use for the skippers, they have a redundancy of declaration to make if they cross borders or go on maritime waters, they have no benefit for the data provided. It induces a lack of consistency in the data provided which is a problem, as this is central to charge the compulsory toll which represent an important part of VNF budget. Moreover, the IWW transport capacity is not optimized: 20% of journeys leave empty as VNF records evidence based on the current declarations made (100 000 declarations among which 20 000 are

empty on average since 2018). This would allow shippers to charge more and to take a better advantage of the convoys already in place.

The objective of CEDRE comes from those observations. It should simplify and secure the provision of river transport data for VNF and give new traffic opportunities for the end-users. To do so, the objective is to dematerialise transport documents between players in the river logistics chain. It would then secure toll revenue and data quality, and then enable logistics optimizations (by making available information on empty barges for example). This optimization is foreseen as participating to the increase of IWT modal share and in IWT resilience offering empty places to relocate cargo in time of crisis for example. The data collected can feed the SCMS and the DT to give real-time information on IWT status.

However, the major groups of river transporters already have a system for the digitisation of transport documents and the interest of such an offer for artisanal boatmen was questioned, so a Business Model Canvas has been realised (Table 3), making the start of discussion with the boatmen easier for VNF.

Table 3: CEDRE Business Model Canvas (source: VNF)

BUSINESS MODEL CANVAS				
KEY PARTNERS Chargers, Shippers, Boatmen, Navigation managers (French, Belgian, etc.), Organization / Professional Association, ICC, Regions, Departments, ADEME, Ministry of Transport, European Commission (DG MoVe, Naiades), Universities	KEY ACTIVITIES Sale of services Own Management of an online site Data monetization	VALUE PROPOSITION -Reduction in transport costs due to optimized boat rotations, by reducing the number of boats traveling empty. -Security in commercial transactions (dematerialized and secure transport documents) improve the commercial relationship between customers and river service providers, reassure potential costumers (move from artisanal type formalities to an industrialized chain). -Internal VNF: reduction of costs linked to the process of collecting and checking data, securing revenue linked to tolls for goods, linked to the collection of data from principals (based on commercial data, therefore authentic).	CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIP Information meetings dematerialized transport documents, statistical queries, KPI Internal VNF: billing data and statistical production	CUSTOMER SEGMENTS River carriers (craftsmen, industrial companies), charterers, transport contractors (industry & distribution shippers), freight forwarders, port operators (private or public), waterway management bodies outside France, administrations (river police & gendarmerie), internal VNF (accounting services, estate management, statistical production, territorial departments)
	KEY RESOURCES Own and outsourced software Construction of a data acquisition platform based on a Keeex solution. Information dissemination		CHANNELS Professional federations of shippers, freight forwarders, river carriers, ports, VNF territorial development services, Norlink, Medlink, Haropa, VNF transport events, e-mailing, LinkedIn, Belgian or Dutch (or even German) counterparts or partners of VNF	
COST STRUCTURE IT (Build+Run), marketing cost, communication, training & support		REVENUE STREAMS Identification of empty boats allows customers to charter them at competitive prices, from carriers who can lower the cost of their trips (lower fuel consumption) and the CO2 emissions of their trips, pooling of the hold. VNF: increase in tolls resulting from better capture of transport data (at sources), and specific subscriptions depending on the players		

3.2.1.2 Use of IoT on the Seine

Several initiatives (experiments, projects) are underway at VNF around the exploitation of the technological lever that is the IoT in order to meet the various needs of the waterway domain and in service of the user.

As part of these various projects, it is necessary to connect to a wide range of connected objects (IoT) that will send back a significant amount of physical data from the field (localisation, vibration rate, water level, temperature, wind speed, etc.)

In fine, the objective would be the implementation of a Data Lake, to build an operational database of IoT (raw data) and a referential of learning data (Dataset). To store, process and distribute IoT data (or the results of their processing) from the Information System, the implementation of an “IoT” Data Hub would allow the concentration of this production data and would include the processing to be developed to exploit it.

In the context of the CRISTAL Project, VNF chose to monitor occupancy and availability of mooring spots, as especially on the Seine, inside Paris, there is a lack of space and not all barges are subject to the AIS obligation, which induce a need to geolocate them. Before the CRISTAL project started, some geolocation solutions (LoRaWAN, GPRS) on the barges have been tested. However, the barges do not have power sources and there is no legal obligation for the barges to be equipped.

Also, VNF have examined other solutions. As part of the CRISTAL project, VNF explores a solution based on cameras deployed on the quays (detailed figure 4).

The service could be offered free of charge to the manager and users who have a geolocation system that can interface with the information systems of managers and other stakeholders. As well, recommendations for geolocation standards could be suggested and users could finally be informed about the availability of parking and handling areas.

This kind of service is provided in order to increase the attractiveness of IWT. The aim is then to contribute to the modal shift objective of the CRISTAL Project. The data produced by this technology can be shared with the SCMS and the DT in order to provide real-time data on the status of IWT.

Figure 4: Use of IoT scheme (source: VNF).

3.2.2. Tools for maintenance

In this second section, three tools are going to be described. They all have the aim to improve maintenance on French River Pilot which would improve IWT reliability. The buoys are developed internally to WP8, while the Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR) system and Acoustic Emission (AE) Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) are developed in collaboration with WP2, along with the Digital Twin (DT) developed in WP5 and will be tested in the laboratory in their respective Work Packages.

The results of those three tools can feed the DT and an evaluation of the relevance of the numerical models and their mode of entry could be carried out.

VNF could use the results to feed into the maintenance, renovation and modernization program that are currently carried out.

3.2.1.3 *Flood management on the Moselle river*

The Moselle River with a large gauge, in its developed parts, is equipped with lateral buoys (128 in total). These buoys are subject to various contingencies that can lead to their displacement or even drift (floods, jams, collisions). This drift can provoke incident as ships use those buoys to guide themselves into the waterway. Regardless of the origin of the damage to the integrity of the marking, the aim is to establish the report, organize the information to the user, and take corrective measures as soon as possible.

Different needs have been established:

- Know the real-time position of the buoys.
- Trigger an alarm in case of dragging.
- Notify the user by disseminating the information through existing channels.
- Plan the interventions to put the buoys back in place.

To do so, remote monitoring/remote management of the buoys and automation of information dissemination should be put in place. The project consists of the installation of connected lights, compatible with the existing buoy model, which complement and improve the visibility of these buoys at night and in foggy weather.

The light is equipped with a GPS card, a GSM modem and can be remotely monitored. It is self-powered.

A gateway regularly interrogates the light, checks its position and status, and in the event of a dragging alert, generates a pre-formatted message type AvisBat notice (notice to skippers VNF website) and sends SMS and email alarms (see Figure 5).

The objective is to carry out the experiment on the cross-border reach of Apach, a narrow channel with regularly degraded buoys (due to floods, jams, boats, etc.). The AvisBat notice will be standardized, and the prioritization of buoy equipment will be studied for deployment.

Finally, a report will be produced in order to propose a format of smart buoys.

These buoys will allow VNF to improve the maintenance of its waterways, especially by improving the safety of its end-users and securing the waterway faster than before. It takes then part of the objective of the CRISTAL Project of increasing the reliability of IWT.

Figure 5: smart buoys scheme (source: VNF).

3.2.1.4 *Subsurface Inspection Radar (developed in WP2)*

Transfer of technology from the rail industry has been applied in WP2 to develop a radar based non-destructive sub-surface inspection system for examination of waterway infrastructure. The Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR) system should be tested in the pilots to provide data and information regarding the effectiveness and potential usefulness of the system tested and evaluated in the operational environment.

The test inspection will be carried out on a lock wall.

VNF could use this information to feed into the maintenance, renovation, and modernization programme. VNF currently aims at increasing preventive maintenance compared to corrective maintenance as stated above in section 2.4 and a better knowledge of its infrastructure is the best way to avoid corrective maintenance which is more expensive than preventive maintenance.

The direct aim of this technology is to increase IWT reliability.

3.2.1.5 Acoustic Emission SHM (developed in WP5)

The AE has already been applied and tested in VNF Lyon’s Couzon lock in May 2023. During the visit the AE system has been deployed on waterlock’s gate and the following measurements has been taken for further process of them:

- Several open-close operations of the gates to record the acoustic emissions of normal gate operation.
- Several gate recordings of acoustic emissions on short gate operations with sudden stops as an attempt the normal operation of the gate for some reason to fail (a general failure).
- Various and multiple Pencil Lead Breaks nearby sensors placements validating the good signal reception.

Figure 6: display of the actual deployment of the AE system along with an illustration of the models and their connection with the Data Management system (source: CERTH).

Figure 7: display of the actual deployment of the AE system (source: CERTH).

The measurements will allow to build a model that will map the good, normal points of gate's operation and the presence of abnormal areas of operation will indicate an upcoming abnormal stat. This along with a second model scanning for metal micro cracks will constitute the overall model used for failure prediction.

This confidence level of gate failure will be fed through the Data Management to the DT and thereon through the DT to be communicated to the corresponding. This technology aims directly at improving maintenance on the network, with the objective to increase IWT reliability.

3.2.2 DT, SCMS & VNF information system

The previous sections are developing tools that will all emit data, valuable data that will feed DT and SCMS. In this section will be described VNF's information system (planning and real time) which covers different aspects as infrastructure (operation, maintenance and asset management), water management, user's information, ports information and railway information. This information system, as well as the tools described above will feed with data DT and SCMS that could both be of great use for VNF.

For the DT, the expectation is for it to produce guidance for maintenance purposes: to predict failures and allow infrastructure managers like VNF to anticipate break and minimise its costs of maintenance.

For the SCMS, the expectation is for it to produce a better service to IWW end-user, especially by giving alternative routes for logistics in case of event on the initially planned route.

Both should be targeted in helping in case of ice jams and improving water and traffic management.

The possibilities envisaged for those two technologies are going to be discussed in the second part of 2024.

3.2.2.1 Infrastructure

VNF already started to create an information system for infrastructure data. VNF has indeed a database of structures, for asset management, and a computer-assisted maintenance management software.

Moreover, VNF has been developing a single simulator (in the sense of 3D visualization) used to test a centralized lock remote control station (this test and training platform can therefore be used to train operators of VNF structures in scenarios of crisis management).

This data can be shared on a case-by-case basis.

3.2.2.2 Water management

The aGHyre application, available on the VNF website, allows you to know, in almost real time, all the data that can be disseminated related to water (levels, flows, structure positions, water reserves) that are measured by, or obtained by, Voies navigable de France.

All distributable data from the aGHyre application are freely accessible without authentication.

They can be consulted in the form of tables and graphs through the list of sites, dashboards, or the GIS (Geographic Information System) of VNF.

In order to optimize its hydraulic management, particularly in the context of the increasing effects of climate change, VNF renewed on January 12, 2023, its partnership with Météo France dedicated to the management of the river network (VNF, 2023). For VNF, it is a question of benefiting from detailed meteorological information, adapted to its network in order to optimize its management in the face of the climatic challenges encountered (floods, low water levels).

In addition, a partnership with INRAE has been set up. VNF is taking part in two research projects in order to improve its knowledge of hydro-climatic projections in the medium term, including the effects of climate change. The PREMHYCE project makes possible to have flow forecasts for watercourses at a low water level. The performance of the tool as a decision support tool has been studied by VNF and also integrated into the national EXPLORE 2 project which is a continuation of the EXPLORE 2070 project. It aims to produce new hydro-climatic projections for France by 2100 on the basis of the most recent results of the IPCC and with more robustness.

Moreover, in order to strengthen cooperation between VNF and SCHAPI (Central Hydrometeorology and Flood Forecasting Support Service), a partnership agreement was signed on October 23, 2019. As part of this agreement, work adaptation of the databases was carried out to allow mutual provision of data in real time for better flood management.

An international working group has been set up through the EEIG Seine-Scheldt, to deal specifically with water management on the scale of the 1,100 km of this wide-gauge navigable axis between the Seine basin and the ports of Dunkirk and Northern Europe. It brings together technical specialists from VNF, the Service public de Wallonie and De Vlaamse Waterweg.

For 2023 VNF has set up an automatic data flow transmission system, which is updated every hour, in the digital system of the Ministry of the Interior for decision support for crisis situations. Thanks to this technique, the ministry's crisis unit is autonomous in retrieving geographically determined notices to skippers concerning the insufficiency of water resources and can put in place the necessary measures to meet their needs.

3.2.2.3 User's information

The data for the information of users is made available on a European portal (<https://eurisportal.eu>) to the European RIS standard.

EuRIS presents all the waterways and traffic information of thirteen European countries on maps or in tables, with

- a real-time traffic image
- information on the position of the boats according to one's rights
- notices to skippers
- water levels, flows, free heights under bridges, moorings in real time
- information on waterways, bridges, locks, berths, terminals...
- opening times of locks and movable bridges
- route and trip calculation
- the duration of the journeys and the estimated time of arrival at destination
- ...

EuRIS provides easy access to all useful information for users (marine, shipowner or logistics operators) on the main European waterways. Users can register their boats there and follow their route, receive a message when one of the boats passes a certain point on the network and request information on other boats, trips and loads. The owner of the information manages the permissions to access it.

The RIS Directive provides a Europe-wide framework for the implementation of the following information services: Notices to Skippers (NtS standard), AIS infrastructure (Tracking and Tracing), Electronic Ship Reporting, Electronic chart display and information system for inland navigation (inland ECDIS).

Every Friday, major restrictions to navigation currently in place or planned in the future on the network are made available on VNF's website. Notices to skippers on events, planned or unforeseen, which may occur and modify navigation conditions, are also available there.

Plans for the route to be navigated by vessels can be prepared on VNF's website with the provision of ECDIS charts, navigation timetables and a river route calculation with the list of stoppages, the map of anchorages and the regulations of the navigation.

In addition to the European EuRIS portal, several local websites are also available:

sif-seine.fr (Seine), e-ris.eu (Upper Rhine), navigation-saone-mediterranee.vnf.fr (Saône and Canal du Rhône à Sète) and inforhone.fr (Rhône).

VNF has also published the mobile app Navi (Android and iOS, available in 4 languages), which provides (on all French navigable waterways) the same services as the EuRIS portal, plus a navigation mode (similar to Google Maps, Waze or TomTom navigation devices) which can still be used despite a lack of internet connection.

VNF does not have a specific information system for its programming of stoppages on the waterway.

3.2.2.4 Ports

Port information systems are not harmonized and are not compatible with the information systems of waterway managers.

Ports are not very open to data sharing, for commercial reasons, in particular on the contents of containers. However, there are exchanges with the port of Dunkirk.

3.2.2.5 *Railway*

SNCF Réseau has an information system for scheduled works on the network which can be found and which data can be used. Other type of data cannot be guaranteed.

4. Pilot Execution Plan and Outputs expected

This section aims at detailing the different steps of each technology development. First focusing on the technologies developed inside WP8, then focusing on the technologies that will be tested or validated in relation with other WPs.

4.1. French River pilot Living Lab

French River pilot Living Lab will be developed in order to involve all concerned stakeholder in technology development process.

The objective is triple:

- For technology providers to ensure that the technology meets the end-user needs
- For infrastructure manager to evidence transparency to its end-users.
- For end-user to bring up needs.

The Living Lab will be developed for the technologies that are developed in relationship with other Cristal WP: the DT, the SCMS, SIR and AE technologies and for CEDRE technology.

The Living Lab process has been thought in order to intervene in instances that are already existing. As the main infrastructure manager stakeholder in France, VNF is already implementing what is called a “Comité national des Usagers” (CNU) which is the national committee that gather all the representatives of the IWW users.

This instance has been selected and will be the place where the SCMS and CEDRE will be discussed as it is aimed at creating better services for the IWW end-user.

For DT, SIR and AE technologies which are strictly maintenance oriented, the challenge is to disseminate their potential use inside VNF. VNF is covering a network that represents 6 700 km from very small gauge to very large gauge (class I to class V). This diversity represents a lot of disparate needs, and two instances are targeted to discuss DT, SIR and AE.

First, the “Comité stratégique maintenance et exploitation” (CSME) the committee for maintenance and operations department heads will welcome discussions.

Second, the board of directors of the department in charge of infrastructure works implementation is as well targeted to welcome discussions.

These workshops will happen before the end of 2024 and aim at producing a Business Model Canvas for each technology.

Figure 8: Scheme of the Living Lab plan (source: VNF)

4.2. Technologies/Tools developed in WP8

CEDRE, IoT and Smart buoys are three technologies developed inside WP8. The two first ones will produce valuable data that will have the possibility to be transferred in the DT and in the SCMS. The third technology will produce maintenance data which as well can be transferred to the DT and the SCMS.

4.2.1. CEDRE, a tool to simplify administrative formalities and optimize loading (France, Europe)

The first step of CEDRE has been dedicated to two activities:

- Realise a benchmark of 18 technical solutions which resulted in the choice of collecting data “at the source”.
- Create a proposal to IWW transport companies (charterers, cooperatives, shipowners) which explained that they were asked to:
 - o Connect their IT management system to VNF’s travel database,
 - o Send data, only data of interest to VNF,
 - o Be informed that this data would be sent by VNF to other “beneficiaries” (Haropa, CNR, GPM, Belgian waterway administrations, etc.).

From this first step, 15 companies have been contacted. 15 companies that organise and market the transport services of about 900 boats, i.e. half of the commercial fleet sailing in France.

- Negotiation and contractualization of the agreement with all these companies, expected: by the end of 2024.

While negotiating with them, VNF is creating the bridge between its system and companies’ system.

- Transforming companies’ system to ERINOT format, expected: by the end of 2024.

- Transforming VNF system to open it up to the compagnies, expected: by the end of 2024.

Then this system needs to share the authorized data to the authorized persons in order to communicate on empty barges for example:

- Framing data sharing on “empty and looking for cargo” vessels, expected by 2025 which is the main expected output of this technology.

4.2.2. Use of sensors for the purposes of navigation facilitation and safety

As the use of IoT has been started before the beginning of Cristal, this technology followed the path of the former tests made in order to monitor occupancy and availability of mooring spots.

First, the camera has been chosen and received. Then a first site has been defined: Louis Blériot Quay inside Paris.

The AI has been trained on a road parking (the recognition rate is now around 98%) and the camera has been installed on site. Preprocessing has been carried out on site and post processing is currently carried out by the external company in charge of developing the AI.

Then, the final solution will be post processed in a VNF data hub.

- VNF data hub to be consolidated to post process the final solution and a boat reference database will be created, expected by the end of 2024.

The last step of the project lies in the development of an application that generates a temporary AIS point (for the duration of the mooring) which makes the barge visible in all available solutions. This last step is the main output of this technology.

- Application development expected by 2025.

The development of these solutions has led VNF to formalize various reports and deployment manuals that highlight the scenarios in which these solutions are inoperative.

The possibility to geolocate barges that are not equipped with AIS while advising users on the mooring occupancy are the main output expected for this technology.

4.2.3. Use of sensors for flood management on the Moselle river

For this technology, tests already started as well, the supply was received in early May 2023.

The first test phase started:

- Preparation of the 4 test buoys, assembly of the lights, installation in Pont-à-Mousson and familiarization with the interface.

During the initial observation, the number of unjustified dragging alarms has been declared too high. Then, the supplier developing the buoys has been contacted so that the consideration and management of positions could be improved.

- Return of the equipment to the supplier for modification of the algorithm (increase in the frequency of position interrogation and filtering).

Once received with the modification, the equipment has been reinstalled and phase 1 continued, mid-October 2023. The correction seemed to work; no more unjustified alarms were observed.

Mid-November, 3 of the 4 lights stopped working due to problems related to insufficient battery charge.

- Corrective measures were asked to the supplier.

A deployment in the Apach reach is planned for a second test phase, with a survey of users expected as soon as the buoys are corrected.

Then, data emitted by the buoys will be transformed into AvisBat notices (name of the alerts system to end-users). The work already started to permit it and is expected finalized by the end of 2024.

Finally, a report will be produced in order to propose a format of smart buoys, expected by the end of 2024.

The correct emission of alerts is the main output expected for this technology.

4.3. Tools developed in relation with other WPs

The Subsurface Inspection Radar and the Acoustic Emission SHM are two technologies, developed in WP2 and WP5 to collect data, in order to improve infrastructure maintenance.

Both technologies are first developed and tested in laboratory and are tested in operational condition (on VNF lock) in order to be validated. They will both feed the DT and the SCMS.

DT and SCMS are the main CRISTAL Project outputs and will be both tested in the French River Pilot. They are developed in WP5 and in WP3.

4.3.1. Subsurface Inspection Radar

A radar based non-destructive sub-surface inspection system for examination of waterway infrastructure has been developed in WP2. This Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR) system should be tested in the pilots to provide opportunity for the effectiveness and potential usefulness of the system to be tested and evaluated in the operational environment.

The technology will be tested for the inspection of the vertical walls of lock chambers.

- EUMO is focusing on:
 - Implementing a new technology concept based on pivoting and rotating step-by-step the GPR for multiple scanning of wall areas, which is different to the rotating GPR that was used for rail tunnel scanning and believed to be more efficient for this case.
 - Integration of the GPR equipment onto a system capable to perform the scanning of lock sidewalls.
 - UNEW is focusing on:
 - Testing the new concept in the lab and in relevant environment (a concrete wall like the lock's walls), being supported by EUMO in this activity. Relevant visualisations are expected in April 2024.
 - Developing method and algorithms for data processing and visualisation.
-
- Site visit has been made in November 2022
 - Tests in laboratory and on relevant environment were completed early 2023
 - Lock inspection is planned in 2024
 - Evaluation report on the effectiveness of the inspection system, and the accuracy and usefulness of the inspection data will be completed by the end of 2024

The output from the inspection system will provide information on the sub-surface condition of the lock, and potentially its surroundings (e.g., soil adjacent to lock structure), relevant to those responsible for the maintenance of the lock, including:

1. "Probable" indication on where to look further and what to expect behind an arbitrary portion of the wall scanned (specific problematic areas)
2. Information on potential abnormalities in the wall structure detected during the inspection, including the location of the detected potential abnormalities, and estimation of their characteristics (e.g., shape, approximate dimensions, depth, category of material(s) that make up the detected potential abnormalities, etc.).

EUMO will operate the scanning system and provide the raw data, and UNEW will process the data to produce visualisations of potential defects, for example cracks, voids or rebar corrosion). Subsequently, they will assist VNF's engineers to decide on the probable nature of abnormalities and severity of any defects found in the lock walls.

Assessment and grading of defect severity, to inform maintenance actions, is a follow up step requiring data processing.

All three will work on how to use the data for improving VNF maintenance plans and the overall renovation and modernization programme.

4.3.2. Acoustic Emission SHM

In the context of WP2, extensive testing of the AE has been done in CERTH research institute laboratory calibrating the validating system configuration through Lead Pencil Breaks and ultrasonic calibration pulses.

Moreover, further testing on sensitivity repeatability has been performed in large metallic structures in the premises of CERTH with large metallic movable objects.

The CERTH Institute has developed and tested in laboratory the AE equipment and systems.

- Laboratory tests, validations in early and end of 2023
- 1st water lock visit for system deployment and first measurements in June 2023
- 2nd water lock visit mid of 2024 gathering additional in-site data and measurements.
- Evaluation, validation by end of 2024 and start of 2025.

The measurements will allow to build a model that will map the good, normal points of gate's operation and the timely presence of abnormal areas of operation will indicate an upcoming abnormal failure. This along with a second model scanning for metal micro cracks will constitute the overall model used for failure prediction constituting the output of this technology.

The main output expected of this technology is to improve maintenance as it is currently done at VNF.

4.3.3. DT & SCMS

For the DT, the expectation is for it to produce guidance for maintenance purposes: to predict failures and allow infrastructure managers like VNF to anticipate break and minimise its costs of maintenance.

For the SCMS, the expectation is for it to produce a better service to IWW end-user, especially by giving alternative routes for logistics in case of event on the initially planned route.

Both should be targeted in helping in case of ice jams and improving water and traffic management.

The process will be done by exchanging data with Fraunhofer and CERTH in order to develop these technologies. The typology of data available has been evidence in section 3.2.3. DT & SCMS will be tested on French River Pilot on the second half of the project, starting mid-2024.

5. Expected Pilot Results & Assessment Plan

5.1. Expected project key results which are related to the subject matter of the Pilot

5.1.1 KPI's of the River Pilot

The KPIs below are currently tracked at a national level by VNF and will be used to measure the impact of CRISTAL Project. However, the measurement might not be available at the level of a corridor might not be guaranteed.

Table 4: French River Pilot KPIs (sources: VNF except when specified)

KPIs	Current status
Infrastructure. Objective: improve IWT reliability	
Reliability of the infrastructure: proportion of preventive maintenance (avoidance of failure) compared to corrective maintenance (failure repair)	Target set at 70% of preventive maintenance by 2030 (currently it is not possible to provide quantitative numbers, however, the organization has to increase preventive maintenance (it is compulsory) and the percentage is estimated quite low)
Progress rate of the Hydraulic Management of the network modernization plan	0% completed (Department currently on creation)
Availability rate of the network on the wide gauge	98% available in 2023
Traffic. Objective: improve IWT modal share	
Number of tons transported on the network	43.3 million of tons transported in 2023
Number of Twenty-Foot Equivalent Unit (TEU) transported	605 500 TEU in 2022
Number of freight barges navigating on French network	2022: around 1707 barges (of which 600 are French)
Number of new projects creating a new traffics on IWW	2023: 120 projects
Monitoring of the activities of the conceded IWW ports (sales/IWW volumes handled /all modes volumes handled)	2022: 34 M€; 6.3 Megatons for IWW; 18.7 Megatons for all modes of transport.
Modal share of IWW inside seaports on container traffics	Dunkerque – 2020 – 7% Haropa – 2023 – 10% Fos – 2023 – 5%
Users' satisfaction. Objective: improve IWT modal share	
User satisfaction on VNF corridors for river freight transport for wide gauge	98% in 2023
Clients (freight forwarders) satisfaction rate on river transport in France	AUTF report – 2024: 56% (AUTF & Eurogroup, 2024).

5.1.2 Assessment plan

5.1.2.1 *Technology elements; FOB sensors, WP9 Smart Buoys, and others*

Fiber optic technology does not seem useful on the Seine and Moselle for bathymetric use (no non-mobile hard point for dredging justifying a fixed fattening monitoring installation above the fibre).

Given the development of the Seine and the Moselle with transverse hydraulic regulation works (navigation dams), the needs in terms of smart buoys are limited to remote management on the Seine and the Moselle compared to the monitoring solution developed in Poland.

These solutions could, on the other hand, be potentially useful on the Loire which is a navigable river but without navigation dams.

VNF is not responsible for flood risk management or monitoring. The implementation of these monitoring technologies in the service of flood risk management can be an opportunity within the framework of a structured partnership with the local authorities in charge of the management of aquatic environments and protection against floods, and a partnership with the central hydrometeorological and flood forecasting support service.

5.1.2.2 *Closed systems like AE, Subsurface Radar inspection, and others*

Structure monitoring and auscultation systems can be tools for preventive and predictive maintenance.

They will have to be compared to existing technologies in terms of:

- maturity,
- methods of application: fields of application, practical constraints of use, limits of use, precision and/or sensitivity, personnel, and necessary skills,
- operating characteristics: necessary access, necessary traffic cuts or restrictions, yield and/or sampling, results availability delays, traffic disruptions on the measurements, environmental disruptions on the measurements, risks for users or the public, bulk - weight,
- Advantages/disadvantages,
- availability and cost,
- references available: standards, procedures, articles.

The analysis will depend on the maintenance or asset management process that will use this technology:

- the maintenance of assets (discrete and linear works), i.e. all the technical, administrative and management actions during the life cycle of an asset, intended to maintain it or restore it in a state in which it can perform the required function
- asset monitoring, i.e. the activity carried out manually or automatically aimed at observing the actual state of the infrastructure; monitoring differs from inspection in that it is used to assess changes in infrastructure parameters over time; monitoring is an integral part of asset maintenance

- asset inspection, i.e. the compliance check carried out by measuring, observing, testing or calibrating the significant characteristics of the infrastructure
- major maintenance renewal (GER) of assets, i.e. the action of regenerating part of a piece of equipment or equipment, or the action of major maintenance of long-term equipment of life, carried out with the aim of increasing the life of the good
- assessment of the state of the asset and its monitoring

5.1.2.3 *DT and SCMS applications*

The CRISTAL project will develop a digital twin which is intended to receive, manage and process (algorithms, AI, etc.) infrastructure data.

The CRISTAL digital twin will have the ability to transmit raw or processed data to the infrastructure management operators. It is useful to have medium-term predictive maintenance data and these data could be used for preventive and predictive maintenance to strengthen the resilience of the waterway.

The multimodal corridor management system will be at the service of users (carriers, shippers, etc.) to optimize modal shift and ensure the multimodal resilience of freight transport in the event of crisis.

The CRISTAL project information system can also feed the authorities (in particular helping to disseminate information to crisis centres).

The digital twin is an opportunity to pool European data, to pool the development, maintenance, and improvement of information systems (infrastructures, artificial intelligence, software, decision support systems, etc.), to standardise, to speed up partnerships ...

The ready-made guidelines for the creation of a synchromodal transport corridor management system in terms of regulation, administration, business models and management will be used by VNF to accelerate modal shift.

The developed guidelines of a European comprehensive real-time monitoring system for water levels and hydrological conditions, including RIS, will be used to upgrade the EURIS platform and the VNF monitoring system.

The priority for VNF is:

- to provide the data, allowing a vision of the current and future state of the network (opening/closing, timetables, unemployment, gauge/level of service/water level etc.), to the digital twin of CRISTAL,
- to report information to the authorities (crisis centres, etc.)

Many other data and models could be integrated into the digital twin in the future:

- hydraulic
- bathymetry and dredging
- image database of waterway disorders to train an AI to semi-automatically detect these disorders and thus develop a maintenance decision support system
- maintenance
- coordination of annual shutdown between inland waterway and rail network
- invasive species and drifts/ice jams
- geographic data and spatial analyses
- hydraulic works safety
- biodiversity and water quality
- geotechnical data
- risk analysis of structures for a simulation tool allowing the construction of investment scenarios for all the structures managed
- Infrastructure design
- project management data (costs, deadlines, quality, risks ...) for investments
-

This integration of data and models will depend on the policy of VNF and the French State in terms of data management and algorithms:

- Internal and/or external
- Control and certification of actors and systems (performance, resilience, security and defence of information systems)
- Standardization
- European pooling
- Protection and enhancement of property and usage rights

5.2. Innovation plan and expected impact of Cristal at the regional and EU level

For VNF, regarding to the CRISTAL project, the resilience of the infrastructure encompasses better real-time knowledge of the state of the network. This implies knowledge of the condition of the structures, the state of the waterways (water level, channel, presence of obstructions), and the state of the flows (boats and their cargoes). The innovation topics aim to progressively move towards real-time and then a proactive approach.

Table 5: Innovation Plan by objective (Source: VNF).

Ambition and proposed Innovation	Partner and system
Continuous information updating on waterways conditions and bridge clearance for vessels: IWW Intelligent Communication Hub	Provision of RIS data in the European EURIS portal by VNF Use of sensors for the purposes of navigation facilitation and safety by VNF
Structural health monitoring of existing infrastructures for informing preventive maintenance: multi IoT Sensors and vessel mounted radar	Radar inspection by UNEW and EUROMOBILITA
Inform decision making processes towards a disaster resilient management: Decision Support System DSS webGIS platform	Provision of RIS data in the European EURIS portal by VNF Use of sensors for the purposes of navigation facilitation and safety by VNF CEDRE, a tool to simplify administrative formalities and optimize loading by VNF
A Corridor Visibility and Open data platform integrated to the synchromodal corridor management system	Provision of RIS data in the European EURIS portal by VNF Use of sensors for the purposes of navigation facilitation and safety by VNF CEDRE, after being implemented in the IWT industry, could be connected with existing online freight burses (multimodal) including IA
Synchromodal resource planning and cooperative operations preparation integrated to the synchromodal corridor management system: A toolbox of services for multimodal planning	Provision of RIS data in the European EURIS portal by VNF CEDRE (same as hereabove)
Innovative Governance Model	CEDRE, if connected to other multimodal freight burses, will require an independent governance authority accepted by barge owners, freight forwarders and cargo owners

Table 6: Expected impact of Cristal objectives (Source: VNF).

CRISTAL expected impact	Actions planned in the French river pilot or related to some of the tasks
Ensure navigability for inland waterways by assuring at least 50% capacity during extreme weather events.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provision of some input data to SCMS developed by WP3 and DT developed by WP5 • Radar inspection by UNEW and EUROMOBILITA • Use of sensors for flood management on the Moselle River by VNF
Enhance land/sea/infrastructure resilience to extreme weather and human caused events by assuring at least 80% capacity at network level during the disruptions.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provision of some input data to the SCMS developed by WP3 and DT developed by WP5 • Use of sensors for the purposes of navigation facilitation and safety by VNF • Use of sensors for flood management on the Moselle River by VNF
Contribute with at least a 20% increase in modal shift to the sustainability of transport systems.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CEDRE is designed to reduce the number of barges travelling partly or totally empty, and therefore increase IWT price attractiveness to shippers & freight forwarders
Ensure resilience and smooth functioning of passenger mobility as well as freight transport and logistics networks operating on these infrastructures.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provision of some input data to the SCMS developed by WP3 and DT developed by WP5 • Use of sensors for the purposes of navigation facilitation and safety by VNF • Use of sensors for flood management on the Moselle River by VNF
Increase the use of recycled materials within or across transport modes by at least 30%.	N/A
Reduce environmental impact (emissions, soil/water pollution, degradation of ecosystems and fragmentation of habitats) during construction, maintenance, operation and decommissioning of the infrastructure in line with the EU environmental legislation.	N/A
Development of new governance models that enable cooperation across institutional, modal and national boundaries.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CEDRE, a tool to simplify administrative formalities and optimize loading by VNF

6. Conclusions

In conclusion, French River Pilot is involved in two ways inside the CRISTAL Project. It develops tools to answer its objectives and by extension, the objectives of the project by its own, and it is committed in testing and validating tools and technologies developed both inside the pilot and by the rest of the project's partners.

By developing CEDRE, the use of IoT sensors and smart buoys, and by testing and validating AE, SIR, DT and SCMS technologies, French River Pilot aims at developing a better control on the real time state of its infrastructure and how it is used. Doing so would help developing a better maintenance, more efficient and cheaper, increasing IWW availability rate. In the meanwhile, this increased real-time knowledge will allow the development of new services. This, combined with the increased availability rate of IWW create a real incentive for the end-user, towards a better modal share for IWW.

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7. Appendices

Budget:

only before tax prices	Description of cost	Personnal Costs	Subcontracting Costs	Purchase costs			Indirect Costs	Total
				Travel and Subsistance	Equipment (without taking out the depreciation)	Other Goods, works and services		
VNF funds		133144	148000	0	72000	0	0	242519
Total UE		263500	170000	4000	0	35000	75625	548125
CEDRE	Realisation of the project by a subcontract (HT)		250000					250000
	Personal cost	116660						116660
IOT	anayllis and writing f the requirements specifications (HT)		8000					8000
	Data Hub Development (HT)		60000					60000
	Sensors purchase and deployment (HT)				15000			15000
	Personal cost	116660						116660
Buoys	buoys purchase dans deployment (HT)				57000			57000
	Personal cost	116660						116660
Project management	Personal cost	46664						46664
	Project related events			4000				4000
Total costs		396644	318000	4000	72000	0	0	790644

Risks:

Technologies will have to demonstrate their usefulness to local lock managers and operators.

SIR

Technology operating during operation, at night, while being compatible (performance, health and safety) with the performance of works, the presence of other stakeholders and equipment (electric, electronic, sensors) and incomplete or absent documentation, would be suited to operating constraints.

AE

Technology operating during operation, while being compatible (performance and safety) with the environment noise (works, operation ...), the presence of other stakeholders and incomplete or absent documentation, would be suited to operating constraints.

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